

REASSESSING THE ISRAEL–PALESTINE TWO-STATE SOLUTION: AN ANALYSIS OF GAZA’S 20-POINT PEACE PLAN

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Abstract

This study critically reexamines the viability of the two-state solution in light of former U.S. President Donald Trump’s 20-point framework. Through qualitative analysis of the framework and relevant scholarly literature, the research finds that the proposed points significantly depart from the internationally recognized two-state model based on the 1967 borders, instead prioritizing Israeli security and territorial interests. The study argues that, even if accepted by Israel and Hamas and resulting in a ceasefire in Gaza, the framework would institutionalize a governance arrangement that emphasizes economic stabilization over political sovereignty. The proposed technocratic administration of Gaza, effectively controlled by the United States, may alleviate humanitarian and economic deprivation but simultaneously entrenches political exclusion and external dominance. Drawing on social contract theory and Charles’s “State Building 3.0” framework, the study situates the U.S. approach within a broader model of contractual governance over weak and dysfunctional political entities. The findings suggest that while the framework may create conditions for a nominal two-state outcome, it fundamentally redefines Palestinian statehood in a manner incompatible with the 1967 borders and democratic self-determination, reflecting a shift toward externally managed state-building supported by international acquiescence.

INTRODUCTION

The humanitarian and political crisis in Gaza has come to a standstill after US President Donald Trump announced a 20-point plan. This formula was presented on September 29, 2025. These 20 points are about the ceasefire, the release of hostages, and the rehabilitation of Gaza. Under this framework, Hamas will be disarmed and a US-backed Board of Peace will be established. This article analyzes to what extent this Trump framework will be successful because in the past, the Oslo Accords of 1993 did not succeed due to distrust between the two groups. After that (Rabinovich, 2020) and then (Annapolis

Conference 2007) negotiations failed. The Abraham Accords (2020) which improved relations between Israel and the Arab world. But the Palestinian voice remained silent. Most such peace efforts in the past failed because they failed to consider conflicting narratives. Bukhari, S. R. H. (2025).

Trump's 20-point plan consists of two phases. The peace plan framework presented by Trump was approved by the United Nations Security Council in November 2025. This plan is about the restoration of the demilitarized zone in Gaza and the cleansing of the area from terrorism. Trump's

20-point peace plan includes Palestinian sovereignty and a possible path to a two-state solution. Trump presented this framework at the White House on September 29, 2025. According to it, the ceasefire between Israel and Hamas was its first phase, which began in October 2025. According to the second phase of this framework, the formation of a technical government in Gaza and the rehabilitation of Gaza are the objectives. This twenty-point plan is a transitional framework for Gaza. It does not directly implement a two-state solution, but rather, it reforms the Palestinian Authority and works towards the rehabilitation of Gaza.

Gaza is historically considered one of the most important cities in Palestine. After the declaration of the State of Israel in May 1948, the Egyptian army entered the area. Israel launched an offensive in Gaza, but the Egyptian army held out until the 1949 ceasefire. During this war, the influx of more than 200,000 Palestinian refugees increased the local population by 2.5 times. After this war, the Gaza Strip covered 140 square miles. Filiu, J. P. (2014).

Following the Hamas attack on October 7, 2023, Israel launched military operations against Hamas and Islamic Jihad. Now, after the end of the war, there are many concerns about the peace agreement because the diplomatic process has failed for three decades. As Arafat said at Camp David, "I do not have a mandate to negotiate," it is said that public opinion is important in the success of peace agreements. In this context, public opinion surveys on support for the peace process reflect people's thinking. Cavatorta, E., Groom, B., & Sher, G. (2025).

From the perspective of international humanitarian law, Israel's presence in the West Bank and Gaza Strip since the 1967 war is seen as an aggressive occupation. Israeli courts have confirmed that the Israeli government is in an aggressive occupation of the West Bank and Gaza. The Israeli Supreme Court said that the respondents are occupiers with respect to the occupied territory. Until December 2006, the Israeli judiciary had recognized that the West Bank, along with the Gaza Strip, is also an

occupied territory. Darcy, S., & Reynolds, J. (2010).

Hamas killed 1,200 Israeli and foreign civilians in the attacks of October 7, 2023. Israel responded to the war with an airstrike, and this response continued as a ground war until September 2024. In just one week, the Israeli Air Force dropped more than 6,000 bombs weighing 4,000 tons on Palestinian homes. The attack killed thousands of Palestinians and displaced thousands more. In early October 17, a group of conflict experts (TWAILR 2023) warned of a potential genocide. On October 18, the United States vetoed a UN Security Council resolution. Resolution 5/2023/773 called for a "humanitarian pause" in the fighting. El-Shewy, M., Griffiths, M., & Jones, C. (2025).

Clause 20 of this framework makes it clear that the environment will be created for negotiations on the political horizon between Israel and the Palestinians, only after which the path to a two-state solution will be paved. But Trump's 20 points make it clear that this two-state solution will not be based on the 1967 borders because these 20 points appear to prioritize Israel's security. Because these points appear to provide safe passage for Israeli forces even after committing genocide in Gaza.

Following the Hamas attack on October 7, Israel declared war on Gaza, killing 45,000 people. The Israeli army has subjected Palestinians to unrestrained terror. According to the Israeli newspaper Haaretz, an editorial was published in November 2024, stating that Netanyahu's ethnic cleansing in Gaza was in full view of everyone. Then in December, former Defense Minister and General Moshe Yaalon called the Israeli army's offensive actions war crimes and condemned these actions. That same November, a UN special committee acknowledged that the Israeli military action had the characteristics of genocide. After that, Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch announced that the Israeli army was committing genocide in Gaza. Recently, the International Court of Justice has said that Israel's 58-year occupation violates international human rights law. Verdeja, E. (2025).

The United States, the patron of liberalism and a great supporter of democracy, wants to establish a government in Gaza that will be based on a social contract, headed by the United States, and will include technocrats. This means that the people of Gaza, who were previously victims of genocide, have been devastated, and now Gaza itself will be punished by being politically patronized. The Palestinians in Gaza will not even have the right to establish their own government for the betterment of Gaza.

Trump's 20-point agenda is not a complete solution to the Palestinian-Israeli conflict, but through this framework, a ceasefire will be achieved in Gaza. However, this framework will completely eliminate Hamas and prioritize Israel's security. Therefore, this solution also opens a path towards a two-state solution, but this two-state solution does not appear to be based on the 1967 borders, which is a long-standing demand of the PA and Hamas. This framework has the support of numerous Muslim countries, including Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, Turkey.

The Trump framework ignored the statement of the International Court of Justice, the statement of the Israeli Supreme Court, and all the news of newspapers and media in order to stabilize Israel, even though all these statements prove the Israeli occupation of Palestine and also prove that Israel has committed genocide against the Palestinians. If we look at Trump's unilateral and unfair framework, it proves that Trump is not in favor of the establishment of a Palestinian state.

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the key components of the 20-Point Gaza Peace Plan
2. To evaluate the plan's implications for the two-state solution

Literature Review

Historical Background of The Two-State Solution

In the first century AD, the Romans invaded Palestine and expelled the Jews from there. After Christianity in the 7th century, Islam spread to the region, and the region became part of the Ottoman Turkish Empire for a long time. After a

long time, through the political strategy of the World Zionist Organization, Jews began to buy Palestinian land from "absent" landowners of Ottoman origin. This purchase affected the livelihood of both local Muslims and Christians, which led to conflicts between local Arabs and immigrant Jews. After the collapse of the Ottoman Empire, the administration of Palestine was transferred to the British. In 1917, the British government formally supported the establishment of a Jewish state in Palestine. Between 1930 and 1940, conflicts between Palestinian farmers and Jews increased.

The historical background of the Israel-Palestine conflict is very deep. But this conflict has increased economic, political and security problems around the world. This conflict has arisen for various reasons. These reasons include ethnic conflict, religious conflict, territorial conflict and political conflict. The real reason for these conflicts is the Israeli invasion and occupation of Palestine. This issue became more complicated when Israel occupied more areas and settled Jewish settlements. Israel moved further and expelled Palestinians from East Jerusalem. This conflict became more prolonged when Israel stormed the Al-Aqsa Mosque in 2021. On October 7, 2023, Hamas attacked Israel and a two-sided war broke out. Due to this new conflict, questions have been raised about the possibility of a two-state solution between Palestine and Israel.

In 1917, through the Balfour Declaration, Britain promised a national home to the Jews. From 1922 to 1947, Palestine was under British control due to the British Mandate, which led to tensions and uprisings by Jews and Arabs. In 1937, Britain first proposed the idea of partition, but the Arabs rejected the idea. In 1947, UN Resolution 181 proposed a two-state solution. This two-state solution was accepted by the Jews but rejected by the Arabs because it gave 56 percent of the state to the Jews and 43 percent to the Arabs. Israel was established in 1948. As a result of the First Arab-Israeli War, Israel occupied 77% of the land and 750,000 Palestinians were displaced. Then, in 1967, as a result of the Six-Day War, Israel occupied the West Bank, East Jerusalem, Gaza, the Golan Heights, etc. After that, the PLO's position

changed. The PLO accepted the two-state solution, although before that, the PLO had demanded a complete Palestine. In 1993, the first formal agreement between Israel and the PLO was signed, which established the Palestinian Authority. This agreement is remembered as the Oslo Accords. A Clinton administration mediation offer through Camp David in 2000 also failed.

The PLO proposed the establishment of a secular democratic Palestinian state in the late 1960s, but the West and Israel rejected these proposals. The PLO then adopted a two-phase concept in 1974, according to which a Palestinian state would exist alongside the Israeli state, while the establishment of a democratic state in historic Palestine depended on a later phase of the struggle. The interim existence of two states became clear during the first Palestinian intifada in November 1988. The PLO endorsed the formula of two states for two peoples. The return of Palestinian refugees was declared an essential part of the two-state solution. Gaza was declared part of the Palestinian state, but Israel considered Gaza a disputed territory.

The two-state solution to the conflict between Palestinians and Israelis is increasingly being discussed. According to the INSS National Security Index, 55% of Israelis favor a two-state solution. Another study shows that 43 percent of Palestinians want the establishment of a Palestinian state. The establishment of two states for two people is the two-state solution. The borders between the two states will be drawn in accordance with UN resolutions. A Palestinian state will be established consisting of the West Bank and Gaza. Jerusalem will be shared by both states. Paudel, B. (2021).

The Palestinian Authority supports a two-state solution on the 1967 borders, but the current Israeli government, headed by Netanyahu, is not in favor of establishing a Palestinian state in practice, and is rapidly building Jewish settlements within the Palestinian state. Hamas announced in 2017 the establishment of a temporary state on the 1967 borders, while also stating that Hamas would never recognize Israel. A two-state solution is the best solution for this region because the international community also considers a two-

state solution to be viable and this idea has existed for this region since 1947.

History is witness that many countries have been divided into separate states on political, religious and ethnic grounds. The establishment of India and Pakistan, South Korea and North Korea are examples of this. The international community has always supported the separation of two countries, contrary to war, suffering and genocide. Similarly, the international community should recognize that Israelis and Palestinians are two separate nations with separate religious, ethnic and cultural identities. Therefore, Palestine and Israel should be established as two separate states. Israel and Palestine should be separated to protect them from wars and unrest. In 1979, the former European Community had recently proposed a two-state solution for peace.

The Security Council resolution 2334 calls on Israel to halt all settlement activities, saying they constitute an obstacle to a two-state solution. But the US did not comply with this UN Security Council resolution. Donald Trump promised to move the US embassy to Jerusalem and announced the nomination of an American Jew, David Friedman. O'Malley, P. (2017).

If we analyze the Israeli leadership with respect to the OSS or TSS, the Israeli leadership only seemingly supports the TSS. Asad Ghanem is a Palestinian-Israeli analyst, according to him, the Israeli people and government stand against the two-state solution. Allegra, M., & Napolitano, P. (2011).

Research Methodology

This research adopts a Qualitative methodology that will work with an analytical approach to view Trump's proposed framework in the context of a two-state solution. Through this analysis, 20 points will be examined and it will be seen whether these 20 points have the potential to resolve the Israeli-Palestinian conflict or whether they will only be effective in establishing temporary peace in Gaza. Because the last point of these 20 points includes the fact that these 20 points will also pave the way for a two-state solution, we will cover them in detail. This study relies on secondary data sources, including books, research articles,

research reports, research articles, think tanks, analytical reports, etc. In addition, information has been obtained from newspaper publications such as the New York Times and Al Jazeera. This analysis will provide a comprehensive assessment of the potential usefulness of the project by integrating the insights gained through a thematic synthesis.

This approach is relevant for a complex issue like Israel and Palestine because it is extremely difficult to collect direct data on this issue. This approach is primarily descriptive and non-empirical.

1. Qualitative Methodology Combined with Analytical Approach

This method focuses on interpreting text and context rather than data. This methodology critically examines concepts and evidence and analyzes a hybrid approach policy to determine why one side is being prioritized within the twenty-point plan.

2. Research Focus and Scope

This is an analytical review in which 20 points will be broken down into different parts. When we divide the different points into different parts, it looks at the disarmament of Hamas, the establishment of a technocratic government within it, and the economic rehabilitation of Gaza. The narratives of the Palestinians and the Palestinian Authority and Hamas are examined.

3. Data Analysis: Thematic Synthesis

Thematic synthesis identifies recurring patterns in data, transforming it into new insights. It allows comparisons between different groups, such as security and autonomy. It covers the failures of proposed solutions for a two-state solution. It compares solutions for the return of refugees.

Theoretical Framework

The United States has adopted three models of state building: State Building 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0. These three models of state building are based on different ideologies. The United States relied on the first model until the end of the war, then relied on the 2.0 model to establish the New World

Order, and then Model 3.0 was implemented in Iraq and Afghanistan.

Charles Tilly (1929-2008) – The most representative and foundational figure in state-building theory, especially for historical state formation,

Famous dictum: “War made the state, and the state made war.”

Theory 1.0

State building 1.0 was premised on a political theory of *realpolitik*. Efforts around the world were made in the interest of America because there was no universal call for state-building. Only five states were subordinate to the US ministries. State-building was only to secure US interests. No state was built to improve the rights and basic needs of the people. State-building was done solely in the national interest. America adopted state-building as a means of establishing authority over subordinate states. These methods of America depend on *Realpolitik*, which is characterized by the label of realism.

Theory 2.0

State-building 2.0 was a classic liberal concept. It was based on Abraham Lincoln's famous phrase "of the people, by the people, for the people." At the end of the Cold War, America focused on building legitimate states, ignoring the ruling coalition. In the joy of the end of the Cold War, America reached for liberalism. The four main principles of liberalism fit well for building legitimate states.

Theory 3.0

This theory of state legitimacy relies on the theory of the 'social contract'. The United States will apply this theory to failed states. The goal of state-building 2.0 was to establish democratic states. But according to state-building 3.0, it seems to be based on the slogan of "public safety first". Therefore, democracy is not the main priority in this new formula.

Understanding the two State Solution Gaza's 20-points agenda dividing into five different parts

1. Ceasefire between Hamas and Israel

This section discusses the first 5 points of the 20-point agenda and then the twelfth point.

This framework assumes that if the parties agree, the war in Gaza will end and the Israeli military will suspend all operations. After Israel agrees, the Israeli army will withdraw to the agreed line and the hostages will then be returned, dead or alive. After the release of hostages from both sides, Gaza will be cleared of terrorism and Gaza will be rebuilt in a way that will enable the people of Gaza to recover. All of these points are related to a ceasefire in Gaza, but these points strengthen Israel's security and these points look like a guideline. There is no mention of the Israeli occupation of Gaza or the genocide committed by Israel in this framework regarding the ceasefire and within these points of this framework.

2. Hamas' s Future

This section discusses points 6, 13, and 14.

Trump's framework is based on a ceasefire between Hamas and Israel, in which Hamas is given a clear path if it lays down its arms. According to these points, Hamas and all other jihadist factions have agreed to stay away from governing Gaza and that all tunnels and weapons used by these factions will be destroyed. Regional partners will provide guarantees that Hamas and other factions will live up to their responsibilities.

3. Technocratic Government and economic development in Gaza

In this section, point number 9 discusses with regard to government, and then points numbers 7, 8, 10 and 11 with regard to economic development.

But immediately after the ceasefire, aid to the Gaza will continue through the United Nations, Red Crescent and other international organizations. Gaza will be governed by a technocratic Palestinian committee. This committee will consist of qualified Palestinians and international experts. It will be overseen by the Board of Peace,

which will be chaired by Donald Trump. An economic zone with preferential tariffs and access rates will be established with Middle Eastern cooperation for Gaza's economic development.

4. ISF in Gaza

This section discusses point number 15,16, and 17.

An International Stabilization Force will be created for Gaza. This stabilization force will be developed with the cooperation of Arab and international partners. The United States will also seek cooperation from Jordan and Egypt to improve the ISF. Through this force, the border areas will be secured.

5. Development of intellectual capacity

This section discusses point number 18,19, and 20.

An interfaith dialogue process will be established to change the mindset and narrative of Palestinians and Israelis. Through this reform program, conditions could be favorable for Palestinian statehood. The United States will also try to ensure that Israel and Palestine agree on a political horizon.

This US framework is an effective measure for the ongoing ceasefire in Gaza, but it does not offer a proper solution to the historic conflict that has been going on between Palestinians and Israelis for decades. His framework does not offer Israelis and Palestinians a solution that would allow for the establishment of two states through a referendum or public opinion and the emergence of democratic governments in this area. And neither is the US recognizing the Israeli occupation within these points nor is it condemning the genocide committed by the Israelis. These points are silent on these matters and within these points, Israeli security is being protected and Hamas, which is at war with Israel, is also being given a safe passage if Hamas destroys its weapons. The United States, which was a great champion of democracy after World War II. The same America, instead of establishing a technocratic government in a disputed territory, is going to turn Gaza into an American colony through a 20-point framework, within which there

will be a technocratic government and an international force will protect its borders. This technocratic government will be directly under the control of the President of the United States.

The US framework after the 2023- 2025 war includes calls for demilitarization, international monitoring, and a technocratic transitional government. This US framework consists of 20 clauses. According to this framework, Gaza will be made a zone free from terrorism and extremism. The effective reconstruction of Gaza will be carried out for the benefit of the people of Gaza. The first clause here ignores the Israeli occupation and appears to be acting unilaterally. The second clause treats Gaza as a patient that the US will take care of Gaza. The third clause, the conditional peace agreement, is a sham because a conditional peace agreement cannot be reached due to the imbalance between Israel and the Gaza. According to the fourth clause, the hostages will be returned alive or dead after Israel accepts the agreement. This is a directive in the agreement. The fifth clause shows the imbalance in the release of prisoners, while the sixth clause seems to be a general amnesty-prize talk for Hamas. The seventh clause promises quantitative aid, but the structural dependence is unclear. The eighth clause is regarding the entry of aid without the consent of both parties. The ninth clause concerns the transitional government, which will be headed by Donald Trump. According to the tenth clause, Trump has presented an economic development formula for the development of Gaza. Similarly, the eleventh clause is also about establishing an economic zone. The twelfth clause is about the settlement in Gaza. The people of Gaza will have freedom whether they stay in Gaza or leave. Article 13 states that all military infrastructure of Hamas and other factions will be destroyed and they will have no role in governance. Article 14 states that regional partners will provide guarantees of Hamas' compliance. Article 15 is about the establishment of an international stabilization force. Article 16 is about Israel's non-occupation of Gaza. Article 17 stipulates that aid will continue in the terror-free zones even if Hamas rejects the framework. Article 18 states that the US government will take action to change the

narrative and mindset of Israelis and Palestinians. Article 19 states that the US framework could create the conditions for statehood. Article 20 states that the US will seek to bring Israelis and Palestinians together on a political horizon. Muhammad, I.

The final points of this framework state that if the Palestinian Authority plays its role well, the United States will try to bring Palestinians and Israelis together on a political platform, and the United States will try to change the narratives of Palestinians and Israelis through a religious dialogue so that they come together on the political horizon. The US says that these measures will advance the long-standing demand of the Palestinians, namely a two-state solution. However, if the American framework is looked at in detail, all its points provide a safe passage for Hamas and strengthen Israel's security. However, nowhere in these points is there any mention that Israel is an occupying state that has occupied Palestinian territory through immigration. The Israelis systematically bought and immigrated to this land of the Palestinians and occupied it, and Israeli courts have also issued statements against this occupation. The US also ignores international human rights law within this framework. The US also ignores the Israeli occupation within this framework, even though Israel's own Supreme Court and other newspapers have recognized the Israeli occupation. In this context, it is clear that the rights of the Palestinians are being denied and there is no indication that the Palestinians will ever be granted a Palestinian state after accepting this framework. If there is ever a possibility of establishing a Palestinian state in any place, it will not be in accordance with the 1967 borders.

Reassessing the Two-State Solution in Light of the Peace Plan

The US strategy in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is clearly a proxy approach, whereby the US is protecting its interests by supporting Israel. In the past, the United States has sent troops to various countries to change governments, as can be seen in Vietnam, Afghanistan, and Latin America. However, in the Israel-Palestine conflict, the United States has neither sent its troops nor

attempted direct occupation. Rather, the United States, considering its own interests, has provided military aid to Israel and exerted diplomatic pressure on the Palestinians. Examples of diplomatic pressure such as the Oslo Accords, Camp David, or the 20-point plan of 2025 are also examples of diplomatic pressure. Because this framework presented by the United States supports the establishment and stability of Israel, but rejects the rights of the Palestinians and appears to eliminate the political and intellectual freedom of the Palestinians.

Due to America's neutrality, many of America's efforts have failed, such as America's efforts in Vietnam and Afghanistan, and America's efforts for peace between Israel and Egypt. But this 20-point agenda seems to be successful because this 20-point agenda is directly linked to America's reputation. One reason for the success of this framework is that it is presented to control the current situation in Gaza rather than a long-term solution. Another major reason for its success may be that it has the support of the international community and Islamic countries.

1.1 Palestinian Authority and Hamas

The Palestinian Authority called the Trump Framework a path to peace and stated that they consider it a step towards a two-state solution. Hamas agrees to welcome technocratic government while adhering to ceasefire. Hamas has partially accepted this framework, but they have said that resistance is their right, so they will not disarm under any circumstances, but rather that further negotiations are needed on this plan.

1.2 Trump wants to turn Gaza into a colony

Palestinians call Trump framework a Colonization. Palestinians see the plan as a violation of Palestinian rights because of the widespread destruction caused by the war, so Palestinian reactions are mixed and skeptical. 68 percent of Palestinians oppose the international force because they say the international force will disarm Hamas while resistance is their right. A number of Palestinians call the framework a fraud and demand an end to the Israeli occupation of Palestine.

1.3 The Gaza Genocide

The beginning of the Israeli destruction in Gaza on October 7, 2023 raised many questions about power, law, human rights and global governance, including the role of the international community in the genocide in Gaza. This genocide has a historical background, but in the latest situation, Hamas kidnapped and killed Israelis and foreigners on October 7. In response to Hamas's horrific attacks, the Israeli army retaliated, resulting in 45,000 lives lost and life in Gaza began to look like a valley of death due to bombing. A UN special committee, Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch acknowledged that Israel is committing genocide in Gaza. The International Court of Justice has declared Israel's occupation of Palestinian territories a violation of human rights. Verdeja, E. (2025).

If we analyze the two-state solution in the context of Trump's framework, we will find that this framework does not envisage the establishment of two states, that is, a Palestinian state. Even if a Palestinian state is established in any case, this solution will not be in accordance with the 1967 borders because the framework presented by Trump strengthens Israel and ignores the rights of the Palestinians. Because within this framework, Trump has not made any statement about the Israeli occupation and has also ignored the genocide committed by the Israelis against the Palestinians. Because this framework is unilateral and unfair, therefore, this framework does not envisage a two-state solution. And we also have to see that the majority of Palestinians are saying about this framework that Trump wants to make Gaza a colony of the United States.

Implications

The research is primarily based on state building theory. United States seems to be testing this state building 3.0 theory on the ground. We analyze in detail how this theory is implemented in this region and what results it achieves. America's 20 points are based on America's State Building 3.0 theory, and America's or Formula State Building 3.0 is based on Social Contract Theory. According to this theory, America is making a deal directly with the people without any ruler. Within this

deal, America will provide security to Gaza through an international force called the ISF, and the economic development of Gaza will also be overseen by America. The technocratic government in Gaza will be headed by the American president. This means that the people living in Gaza, who previously lived in a state of Palestine and there was a regular Palestinian state on the world map, will now be under the control of a superpower through an agreement.

This framework is certainly providing temporary protection to the people of Gaza. This framework is certainly cleansing the land of Gaza from terrorism, but it is also giving a safe passage to the Israelis who occupy the land of Gaza, and a safe passage to Hamas who is fighting the Israelis. These points are also silent on the genocide committed by the Israelis in Gaza. These points will definitely bring about an improvement in the devastation caused in Gaza by the atrocities of the Israelis. But a period of political deprivation will begin in Gaza.

America's state-building 2.0 formula relied on liberalism. This formula had failed in Iraq and Afghanistan, so America found a new path, namely, state-building 3.0. This state-building 3.0 relies on social contract theory. According to this theory, a power makes an agreement with the people of any country or state to protect that people. This agreement does not include the head of the people of that state. That is, America has directly made an agreement with the people of Gaza, in which America will establish a government in Gaza and itself will be its head. The aim of this American formula is to increase America's power.

Conclusion

If the framework presented by Trump regarding Gaza is viewed in the context of a two-state solution, the Palestinian Authority sees it as an interim measure to some extent. Hamas also seems to accept it as a temporary truce, but Hamas is not ready to be non-committal under any circumstances. If this framework is viewed in detail, it is stated in one point that it will open the way for a two-state solution, but the path that has been opened for this two-state situation is a two-

state solution that seems to give Israel an advantage. It is not possible to establish a two-state solution on the 1967 borders. For this reason, the Palestinian people are angry with this peace agreement in various analyses because within it, the political and intellectual rights of the Palestinians have been completely ignored, but rather, within this framework, Israel has been given an advantage. Trump's framework will prove effective in establishing peace in the interim, but it appears to be failing for a two-state solution, just as previous solutions proposed by the US and the international community for a two-state solution have failed because the US and the international community did not make any attempt to end Israel's occupation by declaring it illegitimate in any of their solutions. The US has not spoken out against the genocide committed by Israel against the Palestinians within this framework, nor has it spoken out against the Israeli occupation. This is why it is clear that the US wants to strengthen Israel. That is why researchers are saying that this is a US theory that the US wants to keep Gaza and the Palestinians under its control through an agreement rather than direct occupation.

Recommendations

The Israel-Palestine conflict is not just a territorial conflict, but it is also based on linguistic and religious grounds. It is a historical conflict in which many countries have been involved. Therefore, Arab countries should now support the Palestinians on the basis of linguistic and religious grounds. They should pressure the international community, especially the United States, to provide intellectual and political freedom to the Palestinians. Not only should the United States gain control over Gaza through an agreement, but the United States should clarify the two-state solution and establish two states according to the 1967 borders. In these states, Palestinians and Israelis should be separated and the return of Palestinian refugees should be made possible. After making this return possible, the Palestinians should establish their own government in Palestine in which the Palestinian people should elect their representatives and their own government. After that, a Palestinian force should

be established that consists of the Palestinian people, meaning that the Palestinians should be given complete control of Palestine and the Israelis should be given control of Israel. The issue of Jerusalem should be resolved through cooperation, because both sides should be united. The parties claim the centrality of Jerusalem.

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